

Making frugal innovations more inclusive by embracing complexity

Frugal innovation and inclusive innovation are increasingly popular concepts. We argue that an approach that embraces complexity can help to support effective use of both, even though this seems at odds with the aura of simplicity that surrounds frugal innovation. The approach revolves around involving insights from stakeholders from different contexts early on in the innovation process before making the crucial choices that strongly influence the next steps. We show examples how this approach positively affects inclusiveness on process level as well as inclusiveness of the outcomes, while not making the innovation itself more complex or resource-rich. We recommend using the approach in more settings to further verify its potential.

Key-words: frugal innovation, inclusiveness, shared design space, complexity, adaptive, interconnections, design

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1. Introduction

1.1 Global innovation: end points vs connections

In the past fifteen years several concepts have been introduced or popularised with regards to innovations that are related to emerging markets. Some of these concepts are *blowback innovation* (Brown and Hagel III 2005), *reverse innovation* (Immelt, Govindarajan, and Trimble 2009), *polycentric innovation* (Radjou 2009), *frugal innovation* (Wooldridge 2010, Radjou and Prabhu 2015), *jugaad innovation* (Radjou, Prabhu, and Ahuja 2012) and more (Agarwal et al. 2017). All of these concepts convey to greater or lesser extent that innovation can start anywhere and may flow anywhere. Such concepts represent a departure from the view that only Western developed countries are capable of developing innovations and then transfer, mostly copy, them elsewhere (Vernon 1979).

However, most of these concepts do not explicitly address another important notion: in a fully globalised society the multiformity, i.e., different manifestations of the same problem in different countries or segments, and the interconnections or relationships between different problems are both relevant and possibly more so than the mere direction in which an innovation flows or its specific source.

1.2 Mixing in inclusiveness, frugal innovation and complexity

In this paper we present our insights based on the research question “How can frugal innovations become more inclusive?”, which represents an emerging area of interest. Our findings and conclusions do not exclude other answers to that question, but they do contribute to overall insights on this topic.

We consider inclusiveness from two angles, namely *process* and *results*. On process-level this means paying attention to the diversity in the range of stakeholders like different end-user groups and other beneficiaries). We introduce an approach called Context Variation by Design (CVD) that originated in the industrial design engineering domain. That source is less relevant than the general insights that can be gained from using it, so the specific design discourse is only incorporated in this paper as far as is necessary for a basic understanding of what it can contribute. While acknowledging the practical value of devising simple solutions as being the main characteristic of frugal innovations, this approach also explicitly recognises the *reality of complexity* when addressing large-scale - affecting hundreds of millions of people - multiform development issues like clean water, clean cooking and access to energy. Most relevantly for this paper, complexity refers to the high level of interrelatedness in contemporary society. Also, the complexity refers to the relevance of taking a longer term view into account in terms of costs and timelines, and the positive effects of that consideration for the quality of outcomes of early stages.

In general, when a situation is complex, it consists of a multitude of diverse parts, many of which are interrelated in ways that we cannot always see, oversee, understand, or predict (Sargut and McGrath 2011). We recognise that emphasising complexity might seem at odds with the ideas of simplicity or low resource-use which are often associated with frugal innovations (Agarwal et al. 2017). However, this is exactly the thought-step that we elaborate on in this paper.

While interrelations between contexts may not always work out well for direct beneficiaries (Andersson Djurfeldt 2015), this rather means these interrelations need to be addressed better, not ignored or avoided; this is one of our main points.

Accepting the importance of these interrelations, i.e. complexity, requires one to realise that there is a difference between an innovation process that *acknowledges* the complexity of society and one that *increases* the complexity of the innovation itself. We assert that a process that acknowledges complexity does not necessarily result in more complex or high-tech innovations. The difference is essential. We elaborate on this throughout the paper.

In current practice, the pursuit of frugal innovation can result in an attitude that can easily encourage a localised scope, or in design terms one *use-case*. This is likely to hurt eventual scalability to other use-cases (same problem but different locality, target group and stakeholders) because future steps will rely strongly on what was decided to be relevant for this first use-case. The pace of achieving substantial impact is therefore limited. It might not be the intention of the frugal innovator to reach a large scale (Bhaduri 2016). Achieving substantial impact is however hampered if dozens of such parallel innovations need to see the light first, requiring an unnecessarily long time and high costs before any substantial, large-scale, impact can be achieved.

We propose an alternative in order for the *process* of frugal innovation as well as the resulting *innovations* themselves to become more inclusive. We support this proposition with arguments and real-life situations.

1.3 Reading guide

The road towards the eventual conclusions is paved as follows. First, section 2 starts by pointing out the societal relevance of this paper. We introduce the definitions of *frugal innovation* and *inclusive innovation* that we use and leave discussion on alternative definitions to others (Agarwal et al. 2017). We elaborate briefly on why the two concepts do not automatically go together and share our research approach.

In section 3, we share a brief academic overview of the aspect of interrelations as essential element of working with complexity (3.1) and how the design engineering domain is dealing with it (3.2), we move towards introducing the next-step, abbreviated as CVD (3.3), the core novelty that is presented in this paper, and its main implications (3.4). In section 4 we include real-life situations, which can be considered as a representative selection of our data, to demonstrate effects of using the approach. The situations in which the approach has been used have not reached full implementation in multiple contexts yet. We provide the arguments why benefits can be expected when that stage is reached and decided that sharing these expectations is already worthwhile. In section 5, we situate the discussion in relation to existing literature and explicate how the suggested approach relates to the societal relevance question and the main research question. Section 6 then states the conclusions and suggested next steps for practice-based research.

2. Societal relevance, terminology and the main research question

The initial assertion for this paper, which we elaborate on in section 2.2, is that inclusiveness is a worthy aim and should be universal. In practice, however, despite many good intentions this turns out not always to be the case. The societal relevance that therefore lies at the core of this paper can be summarised as: how can we increase the chance that frugal innovations do become more inclusive? We now first clarify how we interpret the terms *frugal innovation* and *inclusiveness*. Then, we briefly discuss the central assertion that frugal innovations should become more inclusive.

2.1 Our interpretation of frugal innovation and its predicaments

There have been many attempts to define frugal innovation, a complete review of which would require a paper by itself (Agarwal et al. 2017). This, however, is not our ambition. Many commonly shared elements seem to be captured by others (Zeschky, Widenmayer, and Gassmann 2011, Zeschky, Winterhalter, and Gassmann 2014), who refer to aspects like meeting the needs of resource-constrained consumers and paying attention to (re)designing products and business models in order to reduce life cycle costs for these consumers which results in functionality being limited and encourages use of cheap materials. Others also emphasise the management focus on cost efficiency and summarise this by the desire to avoid all needless costs (Brem and Wolfram 2014).

Frugal innovations respond to resource-constrained situations in terms of financial aspects on the demand side (low purchasing power of the target group), as well as financial and functional aspects on the supply side (efficient processes, focus on basic functionalities). This combination of drivers is credited for encouraging creative innovations with regards to products as well as business models (Bhatti 2012). For Western companies, it appears to be difficult to find the path to successfully develop and implement such innovations (Zeschky, Widenmayer, and Gassmann 2011), unless they engage in more polycentric innovation (Radjou 2009).

Frugal innovation is appealing as a concept and not devoid of success stories (Radjou and Prabhu 2015). There are however some critical notes or questions that can be asked.

For example, how might one's vision on the exact meaning of "frugal" define what success means (Meagher 2018)? Secondly, frugal innovations often are created by people who want to solve a problem that they are facing themselves (Bhaduri 2016). Therefore, these innovations are understandably highly contextualised, that is, aimed at a specific beneficiary group. Next steps typically focus on optimising the innovation for this specific group, or in our terms, context or use-case. Further scaling in practice is then limited because as mentioned before the initial innovators may not be interested in such scaling (Bhaduri 2016) and if they are, they quickly find that new use-cases pose different requirements. Insights that are valid in one context might not easily be transferred to another, especially if this occurs sequentially. The most extreme version of this scenario occurs when

a one-size-fits-all solution is implemented in a wide range of contexts (Bhatti 2012). Thirdly, it can be observed that the aforementioned resource-constrained situations are mostly considered from a physical and financial perspective. From a social perspective the situation is the opposite: people whose needs have to be addressed are abundantly present and diverse in particular if one does not only consider the short term, i.e. one initial market. This raises the question whether this abundance and diversity might not be somehow captured and used, even if the vibe of frugality primes our minds to non-abundance, i.e. constraints?

From these three questions it becomes clear that there might be room for improvement.

2.2 Our interpretation of inclusive innovation and its relevance

Taking into account the different definitions of *inclusive innovation*, we follow this one: “the development and implementation of new ideas which aspire to create opportunities that enhance social and economic wellbeing for disenfranchised members of society” (George, McGahan, and Prabhu 2012). In short, inclusive innovations specifically serve people who are most marginalised and who have the least (affordable) access to basic standards of living. Some authors focus on the process, advocating strong involvement of the intended target group when developing “solutions” (Papaioannou 2014).

We combine these views and assert that the level of inclusiveness is determined by two aspects: 1) the eventual number of disenfranchised people who adopt a new innovation (i.e., the scale and adoption) which is a proxy for the societal impact, and 2) the stage and intensity of involvement of these groups and respective stakeholders when developing the innovation. Related to the second aspect, we assert that the earlier diverse stakeholders are involved the better. The reason for this stance becomes more clear in section 3.

Why should concerns about inclusiveness matter? To start with, we refer to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that have taken effect in 2016 (Assembly 2014). The process to formulate these goals has been described as one of the most inclusive ever (Coonrad 2014). In terms of the actual goals, we observed that five out of seventeen SDGs specifically mention the term *inclusiveness* (4, 8, 9, 11 and 16), and several (1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 16) refer to a result “... for all”, which basically means the same. In short, inclusiveness is considered to be an important central element in innovation efforts that are related to international development.

2.3 Why are many frugal innovations not necessarily inclusive?

Frugal and *inclusive* are sometimes considered to be two sides of the same coin because both terms refer to reaching disenfranchised people, and these people often live in resource-constrained situations. However, in practice it does not turn out to be self-evident that frugal innovations are also inclusive (Knorringa et al. 2016).

Building on our experience it is not difficult to see why frugal and inclusive do not necessarily go together. One main reason is mentioned already: many frugal innovations, in practice, each focus on one specific resource-constrained

situation to such a large extent that the results resonate with a limited group at best. This deep small-scale contextual knowledge (Khanna, 2014) does not scale well to serve a wider range of beneficiaries. The intuitive appeal to involve the community that the innovation is intended to benefit seems to inadvertently result in limiting the relevance to that community but not beyond (Seshadri 2003).

Currently scaling an initial frugal innovation success to different circumstances would, as shown in practice many times, require continuous redesign, and thereby push up costs and timelines. Alternatively, a generic design assumes that needs should be similar enough to be served by that same solution. In practice this means nobody is really served well or at all and large scale adoption falters. Therefore both strategies with their focus on the short term hurt the (financial) viability of initiatives. The following example-domain is an illustration:

Clean cook stoves: Isolated successes vs achieving scale

The past decades clean cook stove projects have been executed in many different countries because improving cook stoves has desirable effects on health, the environment, fuel costs, and time spent on collecting fuels. It is estimated that three billion people worldwide are affected by side effects from cooking, resulting in four million deaths (WHO 2016), and more than 100 million Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) per year (ESMAP 2015), elevating this topic on the international development agenda.

Relative to the number of years and projects that cook stoves have been a focus, these projects have achieved only limited success. There are two reasons for this: 1) non-user-centred design (Thacker, Barger, and Mattson 2014, Kersten et al. 2017, Diehl et al. 2018); and 2) putting out a simple one-size-fits-all, mass-produced stove to improve affordability (Pitav and Bhattacharyya 2014). These two factors resulted in low adoption and/or satisfaction rates.

As a response, many projects were started where user-centred design was the core element of the strategy, thus addressing the first weakness. This did improve the user satisfaction in general. However, because the (frugal) designs were in most cases fully tailored to a small, specific user group eventual overall adoption numbers were only marginally better than before.

A recent estimate regarding distributed cook stoves shows some progress. But as acknowledged, many stoves are “distributed” mostly via donor funded programs, which does not equal “accepted and adopted by the market” (GACC 2016). The quantitative results (82 million stoves distributed, out of which 23 million are labelled as both clean as well as efficient) are still modest in light of the total scale of the problem and also say little about actual user satisfaction.

The case of clean cook stoves is an example how in the process of developing frugal innovations, the focus on a specific beneficiary group might be as well intended as it is non-conducive to reach a wide range of beneficiary groups (Kaplinsky 2011). This is a widely recognised problem, not just for cook stoves (Meagher and Lindell 2013).

2.4 Main research question and approach for this paper

To remind the reader of the main guiding research question for this paper we restate it here: how can frugal innovations become more inclusive?

Our research approach consists of qualitative reflection based both on literature research and real-life case examples. The cases have not reached full implementation stage yet so we share arguments to support the expectation of achieving the benefits, i.e. potential for scaling to multiple use-cases. These circumstances do not lend itself to statistical or other parametric analysis.

3. Towards a suggested next-step approach

For a better understanding of the origination of the approach we briefly discuss the main drivers and inspiration areas, in particular the notion of global interconnectedness (3.1) and the way how the design domain considers this while still leaving room for further improvement (3.2). A proposal how to take next steps for this improvement to materialise is then outlined in 3.3 followed by a first preview of the implications in 3.4.

3.1 A globalised society: interconnections are the essence of complexity

To start answering the main research question, we suggest to acknowledge the relevance of the notion of complexity. Once again, “complexity” does *not refer* to the innovations themselves but to the overarching globalised and *interconnected* society in which the innovation should find its place.

Much has been written with regards to the characteristics and consequences of interconnections. (Stacey 1996) asserts that order in a complex system depends on the connections. Because the behaviour of the ‘system’ is unpredictable we need to look for patterns. Patterns are properties of connections, or interrelations, not of the individual data or insights. Likewise (Wheatley 1998) also mentions that patterns are a manifestation of the web, not the parts. This seems to imply that if you focus too much on single parts you miss the patterns. Indeed, when one wants to spot novel patterns, variety and synergy it is necessary to draw in intelligence from remote nodes in a network (Pascale 1999). When faced with complexity, it is desirable to foster ability and attention for flexibility and adaptability and having too narrow a focus reduces this ability (Levy 1994). In the context of sustainable development, it is not productive to search for a perfect equilibrium, e.g. one optimal solution, but instead focus on the capacity to respond, adapt and explore new options (Allen 1998). This represents a learning ability that creates a probability space where payoffs are generated by interactions with other populations. The overarching goal to work with such complexity is not to compress or simplify it as this ignores reality (Chia 1998).

3.2 How is the design domain dealing with complexity

Some believe that the design (engineering) domain is well suited to deal with complexity in societal challenges (Buchanan 1992, Cross 2001). We, therefore, briefly discuss what we might learn from the design domain and how we might take these insights to the next level. To achieve this it is not necessary to discuss in detail what the design (engineering) domain is, we suffice with outlining the main existing thoughts and practices when it comes to dealing with complexity.

Design as a discipline has paid some lip-service to the concept of complexity. A term that is often used in this respect is *design thinking*. Some believe this is the

quintessential mode of thinking to enable people to deal with complexity (Brown 2008). Others call it a “trendy but murky problem solving concept” (Korn and Silverman 2012). Most seem to agree that design engineers through their individual talent, professional education, or both, can contribute to grasping complex challenges.

In that respect the most important aspects to consider are, firstly the fact that “design” no longer revolves around shaping forms and producing artefacts (Nelson and Stolterman 2003, Latour 2009). Instead designers nowadays more broadly look at a problem or general situation and with little pre-conceived notion of a solution start to interpret the situation, something called (re)framing (Paton and Dorst 2011, Dorst 2015). Secondly, especially since the end of the 1980s they tend to take a user-centred approach (Norman 1988). Furthermore the more systemic they work (Jones 2014), the more they include other stakeholder perspectives as well, on the road towards products (in a broad sense) that can help to address the problem. Thirdly, designers can provide typical design skills like materialisation (Lindgaard and Wesselius 2017) and visualisation (Verganti 2017) which help to create for example Gigamaps (Sevaldson 2011) or synthesis maps (Jones and Bowes 2017) that actively attempt to show connections and patterns. Fourthly, the ability to improvise and synthesise is a typical quality for designers (Sevaldson 2009). This implies processes for open planning, tolerance for ambiguity and operating with several models simultaneously (Jones 2014). This is however not yet common practice, even in the design field (Sevaldson 2009). Finally, designers are familiar with the notion of a Fuzzy Front End (Reinertsen and Smith 1991, Smith and Reinertsen 1998), representing a non-linear start of the investigative process, where much is still open, and promising directions emerge from a combination of interdependent activities (Kim and Wilemon 2002).

This brief description serves as background to better understand how these notions from the design discourse provide both a basis as well as room for improvement for a next-step approach in dealing with complexity.

3.3 Towards a next-step approach

The starting point of this approach would need to be the explicit acknowledgement of complexity while not running towards easy answers. This is reflected in the following train of thought: our society is increasingly interconnected, addressing a problem in an interconnected society by means of early scoping (simplification) cannot result in effective systemic innovations and simplifying problems early on to make them more manageable also implies that you are potentially throwing away good opportunities to construct a rich intelligence; furthermore one cannot predict beforehand which specific data and interconnections are most relevant for a specific problem. This implies that in a contemporary inherently complex reality, simplified solutions for an intentionally limited scope have limited relevance when addressing a large-scale issue.

An alternative approach would be to explicitly consider relationships between contexts and to intentionally, i.e. by design, combine intelligence from these contexts at an early stage. As asserted (Dorst 2015), diversity in framing can be

helpful in a solution-finding process. We would like to formulate this even more explicitly: bringing together and actively combining insights from different contexts when developing new innovations to address the issue at hand will lead to better results than keeping use-cases separate out of fear of making the design challenge too complex. Interestingly, designers do experience that design outcomes improve after several iterations, i.e., when taking into account new insights, but generally do not translate this into an approach in which they actively solicit these insights earlier.

Using a diversity of sources is not a new concept. The relevance of multi-disciplinary teams (Leavy 2012) or sourcing in diverse information when dealing with inherently unpredictable events (Tetlock and Gardner 2016) are known. Emphasising the relevance of interaction that is fuelled by diversity of thought has indeed been recognised as one of the key principles when trying to work in complex situations (Sargut and McGrath 2011).

However, for a concrete (product) innovation process that aims to address a globally relevant topic, it would constitute an explicit addition if one would let the insights from *multiple contexts intentionally interact* with each other early on in the (design) process, especially if this would occur before the actual design task and therefore scope has been formulated (Kersten, Diehl, and Van Engelen 2018a). We do not refer to high level geo-political negotiations, where a multi-context stakeholder involvement is the only possible option. For a more practically oriented innovation process, the intentional early stage combination of insights can however be seen as a logical evolutionary, and necessary, step to address complex challenges.

3.4 Implications of a next-step approach

An approach that represents this step is called Context Variation by Design (CVD). The approach encourages to consider problems and develop innovations in a way that *uses complexity* in order for a wide(r) range of beneficiaries to actually benefit from it. The main point: don't rush towards solutions, and even before defining the problem that you want to address, do not just involve different stakeholders, but involve different stakeholders and beneficiaries from a *multitude of contexts* and explicitly bring their insights together in the same design space. One might informally call this "look before you leap", or perhaps more aptly "look in multiple directions before you cross the street".

In the context of frugal innovation it is important to (re)state that acknowledging and using complexity does *not* mean that the eventual result of the design process, i.e., the product or 'solution' is complex, let alone high tech. The cases in section 4 will help to demonstrate this point.

One main point that can be demonstrated with the arguments and cases in this paper (section 4) is the value that is generated in the conceptual space where diverse insights are brought together and made to interact—the shared design space as opposed to the immediate emphasis on one use-case, which has also been called head's down design (Meyerson 2015). Instead, the direct result of the interaction in the shared design space is that any innovation direction coming out of it is, as the cases will demonstrate, comparatively richer and better

informed than approaches focusing on only one context (Kersten et al. 2016, Kersten, Diehl, and Crul 2017, Kersten et al. 2017).

A second result is that the innovations are not one-size-fits-all but do emerge from a shared basis. This nuance allows for more diverse contextual variations than an approach that creates a path-dependency based on the first version (Jones 2015b). Another possible outcome is the connected implementation of variations that form a consistent whole in which variations strengthen each other, e.g. “buy one give one” business models. Such result is only possible if the interrelations between contexts are considered from the start. In all cases, the design architecture that is created through this intentional multi-stakeholder, multi-context driven process is adaptive to a wide range of (known and yet unknown) requirements. Therefore, it is more likely to serve the needs of more (diverse) beneficiaries with comparatively little effort which in turn is likely to positively affect the scalability (Kersten and Diehl 2015, Kersten et al. 2017). This thereby helps achieving better performance as measured by metrics that monitor longer term, and therefore more lasting, results.

In terms of differences with general innovation paradigms the suggested approach challenges both the more traditional stage-gate type models (Cooper 2008) as well as the increasingly popular lean approach (Ries 2011) that focuses on quick first results validated with the focus user-group. Both do not explicitly encourage to consider possible interconnections between use-cases and the potential synergy that can be achieved by this.

4 Examples from real-life situations

At this point in the paper it is useful to support the conceptual discussion with concrete examples from practice. All situations are presented in exactly the same way, and follow a logical sequence. This allows readers to assess for themselves how bringing together insights from multiple use-cases early on can reveal less obvious patterns compared with focusing on one use-case and user group. This provides the basis to understand how these patterns resulted in (design) decisions that allow inclusive scaling towards multiple user groups without *fundamental* changes having to be made.

Like mentioned in section 1.3, amongst others because of the timing of this paper we cannot yet present results from implementation in multiple contexts. We therefore focus on the first step and then argue the expected benefits of the approach compared with other strategies. By doing so, we provide timely feed-in to interested practitioners and researchers. To address concerns that an approach that *respects* real-life complexity results in complex or high-tech products, we discuss this aspect for each case.

To respect the early stage of development of the (small) involved companies, specific details about the products, countries and companies are not included. These details are not necessary to convey the main points.

Real-life situation 1: positioning in a sanitation project Main elements of the case including mono-context insights

- Project addressed public sanitation in an emerging economy for several types of communities (use cases), so already relatively 'inclusive'. The different communities yielded quite different main insights.
- Research in community 1 revealed that operating sanitation units is more durable if there is a caretaker, but it was not evident who would want this public cleaning job with a questionable image.
- Research in community 2 revealed that caretakers require a substantial revenue stream; offering people access to a toilet is not likely to be sufficient.
- Research in community 3 revealed that experiments with sanitation products like soap and water seemed to be appreciated by inhabitants who visited existing sanitation facilities.
- Research in community 4 revealed that when the caretaker role is positioned as being an entrepreneur instead of a cleaning job, it attracts different people.

Likely design decisions when focusing on one use-case

When each individual community would be served separately the designs of the intervention would have been geared towards satisfying the main insight for that community. For example, in community 1 the focus might have been on a recruitment campaign to attract caretakers, while for community 3 the focus would have been to make hygienic products available in the sanitation units.

Rich pattern

Once the contextual insights were brought together, a new, rich, interconnected pattern emerged: giving the role of caretaker an entrepreneurial spin is likely to create new opportunities to properly manage the sanitation units. However, to be able to *position* the job as entrepreneurial, it must *look and be* entrepreneurial.

Design choices based on the rich pattern

Based on that shared insight (pattern), it was decided to expand the lay-out of the units with counters and sun-protection roofs. In that way, the overall appeal strongly increased for entrepreneurial people who would run a multifunctional sanitation unit as a (micro) enterprise instead of becoming a cleaner.

Added value in terms of scalability and inclusiveness

Creating the idea for this particular framing (i.e., how to create the entrepreneurial vibe) would have been virtually impossible if the designers would have based their decisions based on a main insight from any of the individual contexts. By considering different perspectives at the start (i.e., being more inclusive in the process), a new pattern emerged as basis for decisions. The components of the eventual 'solution' were all still frugal in nature and did not result in a product that was too complex for the circumstances. The valuable pattern was provided by considering the connections, not the individual insights. The insights had been contributed by different types of stakeholders, improving the stakeholder-inclusiveness.

End result

The project ended with a prototype for the sanitation units, together with an outline for the positioning strategy towards potential caretaker-entrepreneurs. The steps towards implementation need to be taken by the company.

Real-life situation 2: Maternal health care

More extensively described in (Kersten et al. 2016).

Main elements of the case including mono-context insights

- The project was related to a maternal health care device.
- The initial context was an emerging economy in Africa with health care workers as the primary user group. The company realised that there was also a potential market in Western countries for home use. Including this non-frugal market would improve the chances of a more viable overall business model.

- A first prototype was available at the start of the assignment, the research was supposed to reveal how it would have to be modified for both types of contexts.
- The primary user in the African context would have some medical training and the results of using the device would have a medical status. The beneficiary is the expecting mother and her partner (husband). In the Western country context the primary user *and* beneficiary group would be expecting parents and the generated information would not have an official medical status.
- The peripheral 'devices' in the African context still mostly consisted of paper, in the Western country context they were mostly digital.
- Resolution and clarity of the images for the African context was assumed to be more important than for the Western country context, posing requirements for the technology itself but causing a dilemma for the cost.

Likely design decisions when focusing on one use-case

- If any of the two use cases would have been the sole basis for main design choices for improving the prototype, the most likely scenario for both cases would have been that the functional features and the data-processing components would have been integrated, because there would not have been a reason to design the device otherwise.
- The image quality requirements in the African context appear to be higher, thereby requiring an upgrade of that part of the technology, making the device more expensive. The only foreseeable strategy to still make it affordable for the African context by itself would have been to resort to a donor-funded model.
- The form of the data in the African context would be made available on the screen (high quality image) and the quantitative data on print outs (paper). In the Western context the output would be desired in digital form, because image quality is less important than shareability of data.

Rich patterns

- By far the main shared insight from combining mono-context insights was the conclusion that in essence the physical features of the device could be the same, and changes could be captured in minor modifications, e.g. a symbol indicating the right side up, that would be sensible for both contexts.
- In addition, the main differences between the contexts were in the area of storing, selecting and displaying data and how to make them accessible.
- A high resolution in the Western context was not a necessity but still a nice to have for advanced forms of use of the data.
- In the African context, men (husbands) did, following the contextual customs, not initially participate in the research. When being made aware of the discussions in the Western context, in several cases the husbands were getting more interested and did start to participate, creating a richer palette of insights.

Design choices based on the rich patterns

- One main design choice was the decision to separate the physical features from the ones that had to do with data processing. The latter could be arranged in software and would therefore not affect the physical device itself. Together with the finding that there were no physical features that had to be included exclusively for one of either context, this implied that the hardware part of the device could be the same for the different use-cases, which would make it cheaper to produce. The main differences could be captured in software.
- One less fundamental but striking design choice was to cross-feed the paper-based use of data from the African context into a nice to have feature in the Western context in the form of a digital diary for the users (parents).
- A range of scenarios was generated to connect, individually or conceptually, beneficiaries (parents) from both contexts to enhance either the business model, the narratives around the product or both. These were not worked out further at

that point in time, but by having some idea for the directions, the company could prevent starting out with too context-isolated marketing.

Added value in terms of scalability and inclusiveness

- While in traditional terms only the beneficiaries in the African context would be labelled under “inclusive”, the effort to also consider other target groups yielded results that increased the chance that this disenfranchised group could be served at all. The beneficiary-inclusiveness is enhanced via a detour.
- Additionally, because the two use cases varied, the types of stakeholders that were involved differed, being different groups of people with medical backgrounds and mothers in one context, and couples in the other. These differences created a richer design space and are a manifestation of a more inclusive process. Because of the stories they heard about the involvement of Western husbands, some husbands in the African context started to volunteer to participate, i.e. be included.

Real-life situation 3: cook stove matching range of cooking practices

More extensively described in (Diehl et al. 2018).

Main elements of the case including mono-context insights

- Medium-size clean cook stove producer for charcoal based cooking, Asia based
- Charcoal as a fuel is cleaner than fire wood but requires more wood. It is a reality that a few billion people do use this as primary fuel and they cannot be ignored.
- Company has ambition to expand to Africa, but was aware of different cooking (process) habits which are likely to influence many design choices and design choices can influence user behaviour.
- As contexts, Uganda and Ghana were chosen, both representing countries with large charcoal base while having very different cooking preferences.
- Some of the differences included shape of the pans, required range in cooking power (Watts), cooking duration and style for main dishes, availability of alternative fuels, essence of stability (stirring vs frying).

Likely design decisions when focusing on one use-case

If the goal would be to design a cook stove that has optimal technical performance (highest power and fuel efficiency, lowest health-affecting emissions, lowest GHG emissions) it has to be optimised for one use case. The technical features have to be finetuned according to the fuel, cost-requirements, preferences for power and duration (short with high power, long with low power) etc. Once this optimisation has occurred however, the performance and use of the cook stove will be sub-optimal for any other use-case. It then depends on the magnitude and exact differences how sub-optimal, and whether (major) redesign is possible or even feasible.

Add to this features that have to do with usability, like safety, convenience, possibility to switch to other fuel types and so on, and it is clear that no matter what would be the initial use-case, without specific information about other use-cases and/or no immediate ambition to bring these within scope, any degree of covering new requirements would be a coincidence.

Rich pattern(s)

Some of the striking shared insights or patterns that were found since the use cases were investigated together were:

- Required power ranges in part overlapped, but mostly varied in terms of the directions (low – medium, medium – high)
- In both contexts, articulated more strongly in one than the other, there was some demand for being able to switch to natural gas, but only if the (ad hoc) situation – affordability - allows this. When that is the case exactly is difficult to predict although in the wet season the costs of charcoal always rise.

- Preferred use of pans in one context was flat-bottomed ones, in the other round-bottomed ones. Without any specific design decision, pans cannot just be placed on any type of stove, as opposed to when used with open fires.
- Because of different ways of cooking, a wider range of options has to be considered to create optimal draft in the cook stove, to improve fuel efficiency.

Design choices based on the rich pattern(s)

The patterns above fed a whole range of design choices that took into account both the requirements that the different habits demanded, but also 'third options' that would not have been in sight if the requirements would not have been combined.

Some of these design choices, without getting too technical, included:

- Allowing manually adjustable power, from low to high (in Watts). By making this an integrated and user-adjustable feature it was easy and low-cost to implement.
- Simple accessories (e.g. a fitting top-rack) and more fundamental design choices (e.g. place of the air holes), ensured that both flat and round bottomed pans could be used without further major adjustment.
- An optional feature was built in, being an extension for a natural gas hose. The hose would be an optional component that users could buy (or rent) for periods when natural gas was affordable. By not making it a fixed feature, nor leaving it out, the latent requirement was served in a flexible way where the user was in full control when to make this extra investment.

Added value in terms of scalability and inclusiveness

Without this integrated approach, only end-users in one of the contexts would have been served optimally, but not the ones in the other context, at least not without major efforts. The user-inclusiveness and thereby the positive effect on scalability potential of the integrated design is clear.

In this case the diversity of other stakeholders was limited but suppliers and family members were included in a light-touch manner. The main group for this stage however were the women who did the cooking, in both contexts. Next steps can incorporate input from other stakeholders in the cooking eco-system.

As an indication for a broader response regarding the value of the CVD-approach by practitioners: the case and associated paper were presented at a clean cooking summit in Kampala Uganda in 2018. The audience existed of over around 60 cookstove companies and stakeholders. The presentation received warm reactions and support of the participants in particular because it followed a very context-specific presentation.

Participants agreed on the different types of pans, way of interacting with stoves, different cooking durations etc. More importantly the main eye opener was the realisation that they had not thought before about the fact that the design has to be adapted accordingly as well.

Later on in the workshop the CVD-approach was picked up and participants applied it to their own designs. It helped them to identify commonalities and differences between rural, urban and peri-urban circumstances. The CVD-approach helped out in terms of choice for a universal model, different ones or an adaptive one and in developing the communication strategy with common and tailored elements.

These real-life situations all show that by intentionally considering more interconnections between contexts to influence early design stages, the design space is enriched. This enriched space *increases the chance* that superior insights can be created. It is conceivable that some of these insights would have been possible to create when focusing on just one use case, but there would not have been any driver to put effort into achieving that level of creativity.

5. Discussion

The central novel idea and arguments as well as real-life examples that demonstrate the results of using that idea in practice can be summarised as follows: to address large-scale (international) societal issues, it pays off to consider the need for contextual variations of the experienced issue and therefore also variation of the innovation from the start. We therefore explicitly propose to seek and combine insights from multiple contexts (i.e., use cases) at the start of the process, preferably before the issue has been defined in detail.

Formulated differently, instead of aiming for early simplification and (possibly) later variation, we propose to reverse that by intentionally allowing variation (different contextual perspectives) early on to get better information for deciding which simplifications (choices for the design architecture and priorities for implementation) make the most sense (Kersten, Diehl, and Van Engelen 2018b).

We now discuss these findings through the lens of the main research question: How can frugal innovations become more inclusive? This discussion feeds into the conclusion and suggestions for new research in section 5.

5.1 How does CVD relate to frugal innovation and inclusiveness?

At first sight, our suggestion to accept or even add complexity by looking at several contexts in conjunction seems to be at odds with frugal innovation. However, as the cases demonstrated, allowing interconnections to reveal themselves does not automatically result in resource-rich, non-frugal, innovations.

Acknowledging the process to take real-life complexity into account and involving multiple relevant end users and other stakeholders on purpose without automatically leading to complex end results, could be interpreted as “fighting complexity [of the situation] with complexity [of the process]” (Stacey 1996). The direct link between embracing complexity and frugal innovation is the shared aim for identifying new actionable patterns as input for affordable innovations; the affordability also positively affects the inclusiveness of the innovation. These observations have two main implications:

First, because the shared design space makes use of different contextual perspectives, any innovation concept or direction being construed in that space is better informed, i.e., based on a diverse range of beneficiary views (Suen 2015). This results in a richer analysis of the problem because of a better overall understanding of the challenge (Jones 2015a). Considering beneficiaries from different contexts who bring different perspectives is now a strong point and can still contribute to a frugal innovation architecture. That architecture is not likely to be construed if only intelligence from one single context is available. As hinted at in section 2, the use of the *abundance and diversity of beneficiaries* can therefore be embraced by advocates of frugal innovation, even though it seems to contradict the paradigm to reduce resources (Zeschky, Widenmayer, and Gassmann 2011). To appreciate this point it is useful to consider that stakeholders from different contexts do not have to be brought physically together to create rich patterns that allow for the smarter design choices.

Second, the actual results of this process may still yield partially different innovations for different contexts. The intelligence that was used to create these was, however, the result of tapping into collective intelligence. Therefore, the eventual level of resources for implementation in multiple contexts might be lower compared with the scenario where a sizable part of the (design) intelligence has to be mobilised again and again when entering a new context, which is a commonly used management strategy (Jones 2015b).

If these advantages exist, why aren't multi-contextual design spaces used more often? One reason is the role of manageability in such a process. The process as well as the results are less easy to predict, control, and manage (Levy 1994). This is exacerbated by the psychological barrier of executing a complex process. According to (Koh, Hegde, and Karamchandani 2014) many barriers to successful scaling exist beyond the innovator's sphere of influence. This does not mean they have no power. So, what can they do? We continue the discussion by exploring how the benefits of the approach as we see them can be framed for different stakeholders so they feel more empowered to adopt the approach.

5.2 Framing the benefits for stakeholders

To reformulate the question above: how would the links between the approach that we propose and the concepts of frugal innovation and inclusiveness need to be positioned to increase the chance that different stakeholders like policymakers, programme developers, and managers recognise the benefits?

Time-to-Markets: Some popular contemporary methods to develop innovations and manage projects aim to achieve quick and focused success, i.e., quick time-to-market. This may in some cases be achieved, but in complex situations the extent and duration of success remain limited (Ubels and Jacobs 2018). Given the scale of the types of problems that we mentioned it is socially unacceptable and financially unviable to focus efforts on one use-case (Koh, Hegde, and Karamchandani 2014). Rather, we need to think in terms of time-to-markets (product families). Such a vision seems to be in line with (Ramalingam 2013), who argues how embracing the ideas of complex systems thinking can help make foreign aid more relevant, appropriate, innovative and catalytic. A manifestation of this would be to value local knowledge, experience and testing in a more connected manner.

Inclusiveness on two levels: We have argued and have shown examples that by taking multiple contexts into consideration from the start, a rich design space is created in which an adaptive design architecture can be developed (Kersten et al. 2016, Kersten, Diehl, and Crul 2017, Kersten et al. 2017, Diehl et al. 2018, Kersten, Diehl, and van Engelen 2019). This architecture in itself is by no means necessarily complex. Because of smarter timely design choices it can however play into requirements from users from multiple contexts. It is therefore likely that this basis results in lower end-to-end costs and less required time to reach large scale impact, i.e., a shorter time-to-markets. We have not yet been able to collect data to prove this effect, but it would be a logical one. In summary, the diversity of beneficiaries, stakeholders and their contextual perspectives that come together in the shared design space represents inclusiveness on a *process* level

(Papaioannou 2014), and is likely to lead to more inclusiveness on an *impact* level. These arguments should resonate with all development sector actors.

Frugal demands – Rich intelligence: The link with frugal innovation is also multi-fold. By using the suggested approach, there is no preconceived barrier to consider any beneficiary group as a potential contributor to innovation. This means there is no natural preference on where key insights should originate. For many development issues the primary beneficiaries are likely to have resource-constrained demands which are leading. The result of considering potentially diverse demands can certainly be frugal, but is simply based on richer intelligence.

Overarching result: In summary, the innovation process revolves around (social) abundance, i.e., more rather than fewer resources in terms of the insights sourced from a diversity of stakeholders. The innovation itself can be as frugal as is considered necessary. The resulting innovation architecture is inherently adaptive so with few changes can serve actual needs of more types of beneficiaries.

The relationships between the key concepts in this paper are visualised in Figure 1. C1...4 signifies “Context 1...4”, S1...4 signifies “Solution (or Innovation) variation S1...4”. *Frugal conditions* are the starting point. By bringing together insights that were obtained from stakeholders from multiple contexts the *process is more inclusive* than if based on a stakeholder-group from one context. The shared design space, in the centre of the figure, is used to create an adaptive design architecture that is geared towards satisfying requirements for different use cases resulting in *inclusiveness on outcome level*.

Figure 1: Links between frugal innovation, inclusiveness, and CVD

6. Conclusions and recommendations

In this paper, we set out to investigate how frugal innovations can become more inclusive. The main finding based on our exploration is that—perhaps counter-intuitively—frugal innovations can become more inclusive by making active use of *social abundance*, i.e., different beneficiary and other stakeholder groups.

As a core element of the answer to the main research question we have presented and discussed an approach called Context Variation by Design (CVD). We have provided empirical cases and arguments to illustrate how this approach and mindset can increase the chance that frugal innovations become more inclusive. We elaborate on the overarching conclusion by adding and in part restating the following sequence of observations:

1. In particular with regards to large-scale issues current innovations tend to be either context-specific or universal but not necessarily geared towards a longer term, covering diverse user needs. Both types of innovations do not easily scale beyond the context that developers initially had in mind. The innovations can be frugal but the resources to adapt or redesign them so they are adopted in multiple markets are substantial. This endangers the viability to achieve a scale that represents substantial social impact.
2. The inclusiveness of the innovations is thereby hindered because these do not easily reach a wide range of in-need beneficiaries. A management approach that is governed by avoiding “needless costs” (Brem and Wolfram 2014) might not be conducive to increasing inclusiveness, and thus impact, on a larger scale.
3. The CVD-approach inherently promotes inclusiveness because a wider variety of end-user groups and other stakeholders is directly considered in the process of developing an innovation architecture that is inherently adaptive to different contexts thereby serving needs of a wider variety of people in multiple markets.
4. Allowing or even adding complexity in the innovation process by involving insights from multiple beneficiary groups is not necessarily contradictory with a frugal mindset. This is in line with recent comments by (Leliveld and Knorringa 2017). The quality of decision making improves while the costs or complexity of the innovation do not necessarily increase.

The results so far of using a multi-contextual mindset are promising but are merely a starting point. We recommend the following lines of research to further increase our collective understanding of this way of working in practice:

- If resources are available, create more settings where the quality of results based on insights from a single context can be compared with the quality of results based on shared insights. Even if just as an exercise, this could demonstrate the value of the approach for more stakeholders.
- Apply the approach in a CVD-governed process until multiple beneficiary groups are in fact reached by monitoring duration and costs for “time-to-markets” instead of just for time-to-initial-market. This type of verification would require not just a short-term result but a longer term outlook and commitment from stakeholders. Overall cost effectiveness is an expected

consequence of the approach rather than the main driver. The latter would encourage short term thinking.

- It will be interesting to explore how inclusiveness in terms of diversity of beneficiaries can be combined with management priorities like short-term efficiency and proof-of-concept pilots. What type of metrics might better encourage scalability to different beneficiary-groups without allowing resources in the initial stage to increase too much?

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